

Efficiency Calculations of Containerized Renewable Storage System

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Abstract

The efficiency model of a containerized renewable energy storage system (ESS) is derived and formulated. The active cooling component is also considered to provide more accurate overall efficiency calculations. System sizing equations according to efficiency variables are derived and demonstrated.

Keywords: Efficiency, Battery, Renewable, System, Storage

1. Renewable Energy Storage System Model

This paper focuses on the typical system design using solar panels to store sufficient excess energy to deliver constant power to a load even when the solar panels are not supplying energy. This particular application is for a system is constructed inside a shipping container which requires active cooling.

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1.1. Simple System Efficiency Model

A system efficiency model is constructed using the following notation.

Figure 1: Simplified container system efficiency model

The total energy produced by solar panels W_{in} is transmitted with overall system efficiency η_s and overall losses Q_s . The total output of the system is defined as W_{out} .

The following relationships holds for all further system calculations.

$$W_{out} = W_{in} \cdot \eta_s = W_{in} - Q_s \quad (1)$$

$$W_{in} = Q_s \frac{1}{1 - \eta_s} \quad (2)$$

$$W_{out} = Q_s \frac{\eta_s}{1 - \eta_s} \quad (3)$$

1.2. Extended System Efficiency Model

An important concept to realize is that additional energy will be used during active cooling of the container system. The energy will be used during the stage to remove the heat generated from sources such as electronic losses, wiring losses, and other systems.

Figure 2: Extended container system efficiency model

The external efficiency is grouped as η_{s1} with heat output Q_{s1} . The internal overall efficiency is η_{s2} with losses Q_{s2} and internal load as Q_{out1} . The entire heat load inside the container is denoted as Q_C which is the sum total of internal efficiency losses Q_{s2} , loads Q_{out1} , and external heat load Q_H . The internal loads are assumed to be purely resistive loads.

$$Q_C = Q_{s2} + Q_{out1} + Q_H \quad (4)$$

The main power output is now W_{out2} .

$$W_{out2} = W_{in} \cdot \eta_{s1} \cdot \eta_{s2} - Q_{out1} = W_{in} - Q_{s1} - Q_{s2} - Q_{out1} \quad (5)$$

The useful output power W_{out2} defines the overall system efficiency as:

$$\eta_s = \frac{W_{out2}}{W_{in}} = \eta_{s1} \cdot \eta_{s2} - \frac{Q_{out1}}{W_{in}} \quad (6)$$

The total cooling power W_{cool} removes heat Q_{cool} with a certain coefficient of performance COP expressed as:

$$COP = \frac{|Q_{cool}|}{W_{cool}} \quad (7)$$

The magnitude of Q_{out1} is the sum of cooling power.

$$Q_{out1} = W_{cool} = \frac{Q_C}{COP} \quad (8)$$

Substituting (4) into (8) and simplifying.

$$Q_{out1} = \frac{1}{COP - 1} (Q_{s2} + Q_H) \quad (9)$$

1.3. General case

The equations of the previous subsections can be expanded to include several efficiency stages in the system. Equation (1) is generalized to accommodate k stages as follows.

$$W_{out} = W_{in}(\eta_s) = W_{in} \cdot \prod_{k=1}^k \eta_k \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, the general heat loss Q_k for stage k which is outside the container.

$$Q_k = W_{in} \prod_{k=1}^k \eta_k (1 - \eta_k) \quad (11)$$

For a container system with internal stages the general heat loss Q'_k of stage k which is inside the container is given below.

$$\begin{aligned} Q'_k &= W_{in} \prod_{k=1}^k \eta_k (1 - \eta_k) \left(1 + \frac{1}{(COP - 1)} \right) \\ &= Q_k \left(1 + \frac{1}{(COP - 1)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The general system efficiency can be written as the following for a system comprised of b stages where a denotes the first stage inside the container. Using equation (1):

$$W_{in}\eta_s = W_{in} - \sum Q = W_{in} - \sum Q_k - \sum Q'_k - c_1 \quad (13)$$

Using equations (11) and (12) and simplifying further.

$$W_{in}\eta_s = W_{in} \left(1 - \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^{a-1} \eta_k \right) - \left(1 - \prod_{k=a}^k \eta_k \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{COP - 1} \right) \right) - c_1 \quad (14)$$

Therefore, the efficiency of the system η_s is given by the following expression:

$$\eta_s = 1 - \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^{a-1} \eta_k \right) - \left(1 - \prod_{k=a}^k \eta_k \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{COP - 1} \right) - c_2 \quad (15)$$

The variable c_2 includes internal loads W_{out1} and external heat load Q_H from equation (4). The general form is given here:

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{W_{in}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{COP - 1}\right) \left(W_{out1} + \frac{Q_H}{COP}\right) \quad (16)$$

1.4. Example System

The following system is for the case where the load is being powered directly from the solar input and the battery is ignored.

For system with external efficiency stages $a = (0.97, 0.98)$ and internal efficiency stages $b = (0.96, 0.99, 0.99, 0.92)$, with passive load of 50W and external heat load of 1000W, COP of 3.2, calculate the the efficiency of a 10kW solar panel system.

Using equation (15):

$$\eta_s = 1 - (1 - 0.9506) - (1 - 0.8656\dots) \left(1 + \frac{1}{3.2 - 1}\right) (0.9506) - \frac{1}{10} \left(1 + \frac{1}{3.2 - 1}\right) \left(0.05 + \frac{1}{3.2}\right) = 70.5\% \quad (17)$$

The round-trip efficiency of solar array to output is 70.5% in the above example.

2. System Sizing in Terms of Efficiency

Many storage systems are designed to consistently provide renewable energy. The excess solar energy generated during the day is stored in the battery bank and then used throughout the night. These system are sized by use of advanced simulation and meteorological data tables. However, the following simpler model is still insightful.

2.1. Simple System Operational Model

Figure 3: Case 1 in a simple ESS system where battery and load (W_{batt} and W_{out}) are being powered for time period t .

In a simple system sized to operate across a 24-hour window, the load W_{out} is assumed constant. The power supplied W_{in} also has to charge the batteries with sufficient energy so that there is no loss of load. In case 1, for a certain period t hours, the batteries are being charged at constant rate W_{batt} and load is being supplied simultaneously by W_{in} . The variable t is estimated so that the intermediate cases, such as fluctuate charging rate due to solar output, is negligible.

Figure 4: Case 2 in a simple ESS system load W_{out} is being powered for time period $(24 - t)$ from battery storage.

For case 2, the load is being supplied only by the batteries for the rest of the day.

2.2. System Sizing Equations

The energy used during case 2 must equal stored energy in the battery. Using equation (1) this is expressed as:

$$E_{batt} = W_{out}(24 - t) \frac{1}{\eta_{s3}} \quad (18)$$

This energy must be stored during Case 1. The equation of the battery charge rate as:

$$W_{batt} \cdot t = W_{out}(24 - t) \frac{1}{\eta_{s3}} \quad (19)$$

$$\therefore W_{batt} = W_{out} \left(\frac{24 - t}{t} \right) \frac{1}{\eta_{s3}}$$

During case 1, the total power required to both charge the battery and power the load is now formulated:

$$W_{in} = W_{out} \frac{(24 - t)}{t} \frac{1}{\eta_{s2}\eta_{s3}} + W_{out} \frac{1}{n_{s1}} \quad (20)$$

$$= W_{out} \left(\frac{(24 - t)}{t} \frac{1}{\eta_{s2}\eta_{s3}} + \frac{1}{n_{s1}} \right)$$

This expression is important as it demonstrates how variables η_{s2} and η_{s3} dominate the system sizing. Finally, the system efficiency can be calculated by the following:

$$\eta_s = \frac{\int_0^{24} W_{out}(t) dt}{\int_0^t W_{in}(t) dt} = \frac{W_{out} \cdot 24}{W_{in} \cdot t} \quad (21)$$

2.3. Example Sizing

For a sunny country with factor $k = 6$, W_{out} of 1kW, and system efficiencies n_{s1} , n_{s2} , n_{s3} as 0.75, 0.80, 0.84, we can calculate the system sizings and overall efficiency as follows.

$$E_{batt} = (24 - 6) \frac{1}{0.84} \cdot (1.2)^2 = 21.4kWh \quad (22)$$

$$W_{in} = \left(\frac{(24 - 6)}{6} \frac{1}{0.80 \cdot 0.84} + \frac{1}{0.75} \right) = 5.80kW$$

$$\eta_s = \frac{24}{50.1} = 69.0\%.$$

3. Conclusion

The theory of containerized system efficiency has been completed and show some interesting principles. Of interest is equation (15) which calculates overall system efficiency for both external and internal stages where cooling is required. The cooling of containerized system can be a large inefficiency on the system. Furthermore using the results of equation (15), the overall efficiency of a 24-hr system has been very simply modelled. This model helps insight into system sizing in relation to component efficiency. The formulas presented can be used for further application such as marketability, cost/benefit analysis, and design. More accurate comparisons can also be made between storage systems using the equations.